

From Jobless to Green Jobs: A Comparison of Youth Unemployment and Green Economy in Tunisia and Türkiye

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ABSTRACT

Capitalism is a system that historically grows and reproduces itself by seizing the surplus value obtained from labour power. In this sense, the organization of the labour market according to the periodic needs of the system is of critical importance for the continuity of the system. Today, capitalism creates young unemployed people and the NEET (Not in Education, Employment, or Training) status among young people is increasing. In the face of increasing youth unemployment and NEET status, especially in developing countries, the green transformation process and the green jobs that come with it are presented as a solution. This study aims to discuss how the green jobs that will be created by the green transformation that capitalism proposes to control ecological damage can have a counterpart in the labour market through the comparative example of Türkiye and Tunisia. The economic, political and social similarities and differences of the two countries will be discussed with a critical perspective, and the inclusiveness of the green transformation within the capital accumulation process will be discussed. The study uses a descriptive and comparative method with secondary data.

Keywords: *Youth unemployment, green jobs, Tunisia, Türkiye*

1. INTRODUCTION

Youth unemployment is a major issue that causes instability in many countries around the world, especially in developing nations going through green transitions. This study will focus on two specific countries Tunisia and Türkiye, as our primary green transition target because of their shared environmental vulnerability, which intersects with demographic pressures and institutional rigidities. The main problem of the study is to try to understand how green jobs have an impact on youth unemployment within the general dynamics of capitalism.

The green economy has been observed as a workable solution that will boost up job sustainability while conserving the environment. But it also raises the question: how can it provide youth with authentic opportunities in constitutively limited settings? These types of questions are enlightened in this article using the frameworks of four fundamental socioeconomic theories: Amartya Sen's Capability Approach, W. Richard Scott's Institutional Theory, Human Capital Theory, and Signalling Theory. Every one of these frameworks provides a perspective and insights into the mechanisms that could be used to improve institutions and youth. Together, they provide equipment to diagnose the conflict between education and employment, identify structural barriers, and reconsideration what meaningful participation in a green economy should require.

This study examines labour market trends and policy frameworks in both countries to explore how green jobs can contribute to reducing youth unemployment. The after effect to this action is that, that it aims to evaluate whether green employment represents applicable long term strategy for comprehensive workforce development and prolonged economic growth

2. YOUTH UNEMPLOYMENT AND THE GREEN ECONOMY

A Path Toward Sustainable and Inclusive Employment: Youth unemployment remained a challenging issue across many countries, affecting not only the economy of small populations, but also their social status and outcomes. This can be seen in terms of inequality and exclusion. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO, 2021), young people are significantly more likely to be unemployed than older workers

due to factors such as skill mismatches, labour market rigidities and economic downturns (Bell & Blanchflower, 2011; Scarpetta et al., 2010). In other words, young people who experienced prolonged unemployment were exposed not only to limitations in terms of economic growth, but also to disparities in income and social divides. divides.

Addressing the issues required government intervention with the goal of fostering job creation and economic resilience. The first step would be to invest in green methods and creation, which seeks to align environmental sustainability with long-term economic development (UNEP, 2011; OECD, 2012). This can only be done by putting the focus on sectors like waste management, renewable energy, and agriculture. In their article, Bowen and Kuralbayeva (2015: 4) argue that the debate will continue due to the lack of data in this area. They argue that policies implemented in this area will create differences between advanced industrial economies and developing countries and therefore address the debate categorically.

Analytically, the Environmental Kuznets Curve is one of the economic frameworks that suggests that the economy will evolve naturally toward more sustainable practices that will generate new types of employment adaptive to the market or the need existing within a specific time frame (Stern, 2004; Borghesi, 2006). Similarly, the Porter Hypothesis posits that well-calibrated environmental policies can stimulate innovation, leading to potential growth and gains within the scope of employment (Porter & van der Linde, 1995). Nevertheless, empirical studies suggested that the investment notion resulted in a breakthrough that can be seen in more jobs generated per unit than fossil fuel-based industries (Garrett-Peltier, 2017; Wei et al., 2010). However, looking at job creation capacity within many countries led us to find out that national policy frameworks, economic structures, and capital accumulation level are what shape the degree of success of it. In the European Union, for instance, the European Green Deal played a major role in accelerating investments in energy opportunities, emphasizing renewable energy opportunities and emphasizing employment in sustainable industries European Commission, 2019). Countries like Germany and Denmark have successfully integrated a green certification program within their education and labor strategies (Cedefop, 2017; UNCTAD, 2020). In contrast, developing countries often face challenges within the same

scope due to the lack of investment in programs that facilitate the transitioning of youth into the green economy, resulting in an inadequate labor force. Despite these challenges, green jobs have been globally promoted and thus seen as a strategic pathway toward social inclusion and economic resilience (ILO, 2018).

Some restrictions were seen in developing countries and translated into the lack of initial investment, or rather capital, which highlighted the fact that policies initiated by the government and, nevertheless, the creation of funds will be the key for developing countries' adaptability and transitioning. However, this reinforced the idea that only high-tech enterprises will have the needed access to it. For instance, within the context of Türkiye, enterprises engaged in labour-intensive production sectors, such as textiles and construction, during the initial phases of capital accumulation were structured as holdings. After this, these enterprises expanded their operational scope to encompass additional sectors, including the energy sector and mining, thereby diversifying their activities. The sustainability discourse of capital groups such as Sanko, Zorlu, and Cengiz Holding, especially in the field of energy, is particularly noteworthy in the present day. Captivating Türkiye as an example, labor-intensive production sectors, like textiles and construction, have proven to have strongholding properties that fourthly enabled them to evolve and expand, encompassing other sectors through their operational scope while keeping a high diversification action plan. This could have been done only to their initial holding; as an example, Sanko, Zorlu, and Cengiz Holding met the criteria to be noteworthy in terms of being one of the successful capital groups within Türkiye.

Within our scope, Tunisia and Türkiye both presented a high qualification for emerging green economies within their territories for the purpose of addressing youth unemployment within. In Tunisia, investments in solar and wind energy offer promising avenues for green employment (Ben Jebli & Ben Youssef, 2015). Meanwhile, Türkiye's focus on energy efficiency and urban sustainability has increased the demand for green skills (Çetin & Eğrican, 2011; Kolsuz & Yeldan, 2015).

Four movements were the main starters of the green way spreading across the globe. Each of these events led step by step to empowering green jobs, resulting in what we know and

see today. These movements were known as the Earth Summit, the 1997 Kyoto Protocol, the 2015 Paris Agreement, and the 2020s–2050 Vision: The European Green Deal.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Linking Employment, Institutions, and Human Development in the Green Economy: To address youth unemployment, we had to look through different perspectives that cover all types of visions and widely address what we have. These frameworks are known as Amartya Sen's Capability Approach, Scott's Institutional Theory, Human Capital Theory, and Signalling Theory. Together they present a collective multidimensional kit for understanding the labor market and youth perspective from policy interventions and education to individuals' backgrounds and awareness of the green economy (Öz et al., 2024).

Amartya Sen's capability approach highlights individuals' freedom to choose and pursue the kind of life they desire. Rather than focusing totally on unemployment as an economic indicator, this framework draws attention to future opportunities and meaningful experiences that contribute to individuals' long-term fortune. In these conditions, investing in green energy will not only harmonize economic growth with environmental sustainability but also create new and adaptable employment pathways within agriculture and other green sectors. Ensuring wide access to green certification and skills development programs for young people is essential for sculpting the future labor market and supporting an unbiased and comprehensive ecological transition.

In contrast, Scott's Institutional Theory provides insight on how institutions shape the labor market, and it shifts the focus from unemployment and youth toward what the institutions can provide, in other words, the support. According to this theory, regulative, normative, and cultural-cognitive structures will be the main core to shape green transitioning, as job initiatives don't only rely on incentives and need policy support. For example, in Tunisia and Türkiye, institutional support can be seen through the policy framework, public and government investment, infrastructure, and the background

awareness of youth in terms of environmental issues; this will reinforce, as a result, the green economy and legitimize its own presence.

Human Capital Theory concluded that productivity and employability can only be seen through investing in what plays a role within the green equation, that is to say, education and training programs.

The theory of the green economy underscores the significance of providing young people with technical and soft skills relevant to resulting sustainable industries. Without such investments, there is a risk that green growth will be forced by a shortage of qualified labor, which means limiting the impact of green job policies.

Signalling theory puts forward that educational achievements and professional credentials serve as a standard of a worker's potential productivity in the eyes of employers. Within green sectors, qualifications in areas such as environmental science, energy efficiency, or sustainable agriculture function as strong signals that help reduce unbalanced information in the labor market. In consequence, governments and academic institutions have a core responsibility in demonstrating standards and widely recognizing green certification systems that improve youth employment rates and address structural skill incompatibility.

4. YOUTH UNEMPLOYMENT IN TÜRKİYE

Youth employment in turkiye has become one of the critical topics of policy and academic concern . as a substantial body of compositions has examined the issue essentially focusing on its structural reasons presenting policy interventions to reduce unemployment ,and analyzing its disadvantageous consequences for the national economy.

A global and Turkish perspective reveals that the youth unemployment rate often exceeds the overall unemployment rate. The fact that full employment is an assumption that has never been realized is related to mainstream economics' inability to provide a satisfactory explanation of the capitalist system. Therefore, as demonstrated by historical data in the

field, unemployment is not a secondary condition; it is a structural condition that enables capitalism to control labor prices and to create a reserve workforce within its surplus-oriented production system. Moreover, the prevailing capitalist economic model has become divorced from societal needs. Consequently, the production system, labour market and circulation relations are shaped not by societal needs but by the needs of the capitalist system. In such circumstances, the issue of youth unemployment exceeding overall unemployment is seldom discussed in the context of general capitalist trends. Instead, the discourse is predominantly focused on the discrepancy between the content of education and the expectations of the sector. It is therefore evident that the initial observation to be made is that the labour market is not structured to include young people. The labour market's inclusiveness can be attributed to a discrepancy between the education system and the labour market. The concept of green work, which refers to sustainable production processes, has emerged as a new phenomenon with the potential to bridge this gap.

An analysis of labour force statistics published by TURKSTAT indicates a notable rise in youth unemployment in Türkiye in recent years. In response, various policy measures have been implemented, such as direct public employment programs, job search assistance, employment services, education and vocational training initiatives, wage and employment subsidies, support for self-employment, flexible work arrangements, and the expansion of private employment agencies. However, existing research suggests a lack of sufficient data to evaluate the effectiveness of these interventions in reducing youth unemployment (Bayrakdar and Incekara, 2013: 27–35). As a result, calculating the actual impact of policy efforts outlined to reduce problems largely rooted in the capitalist economic system remains a significant challenge.

Table 1. Labor Force Statistics in Türkiye from 2005 to 2024.

Main labour force indicators

[15-24 age]

(Thousand person)

Years	Population of young people age between 15 and 24	Labour force	Employment	Unemployment	Not in labour force	Labour force participation rate (%)	Employment rate (%)	Unemployment rate (%)
Toplam - Total								
2005	11 506	4 126	3 423	704	7 380	35,9	29,7	17,1
2006	11 480	4 095	3 440	655	7 385	35,7	30,0	16,0
2007	11 431	4 104	3 411	692	7 327	35,9	29,8	16,9
2008	11 353	4 155	3 403	752	7 197	36,6	30,0	18,1
2009	11 350	4 244	3 277	967	7 106	37,4	28,9	22,8
2010	11 410	4 267	3 421	846	7 143	37,4	30,0	19,8
2011	11 435	4 347	3 629	717	7 088	38,0	31,7	16,5
2012	11 468	4 215	3 561	654	7 254	36,8	31,1	15,5
2013	11 585	4 431	3 696	736	7 154	38,2	31,9	16,6
2014	11 724	4 757	3 910	847	6 967	40,6	33,4	17,8
2015	11 808	4 946	4 036	910	6 862	41,9	34,2	18,4
2016	11 861	5 025	4 048	977	6 836	42,4	34,1	19,4
2017	11 875	5 144	4 086	1 058	6 731	43,3	34,4	20,6
2018	11 785	5 186	4 147	1 039	6 599	44,0	35,2	20,0
2019	11 667	5 193	3 887	1 307	6 473	44,5	33,3	25,2
2020	11 711	4 597	3 451	1 145	7 114	39,2	29,5	24,9
2021	11 956	4 983	3 855	1 128	6 973	41,7	32,2	22,6
2022	12 005	5 264	4 240	1 024	6 742	43,8	35,3	19,4
2023	11 831	5 395	4 455	940	6 436	45,6	37,7	17,4
2024	11 678	5 506	4 609	897	6 172	47,2	39,5	16,3

(TURKSTAT. (2024). Labour Force Statistics)

NEET (Not in Education, Employment, or Training) statistics reveal considerable disparities between Türkiye and OECD averages. For individuals aged 15-19, Türkiye's NEET rate stands at 16.68%, more than double the OECD average of 8.02%. The gap widens further in the 20-24 age group, where Türkiye reaches 33.29% compared to the OECD average of 14.31%. Overall, the combined NEET rate for individuals aged 15-29 is 27.93% in Türkiye, significantly exceeding the OECD average of 12.64% (OECD, 2022).

A significant gender gap becomes evident when NEET rates are examined by gender. Young women in Türkiye face a considerable disadvantage: 45.25% of women aged 20-24 are classified as NEET, compared with only 15.33% in OECD countries. Likewise,

39.03% of Turkish women aged 15-29 are neither employed, in education, nor in training, exceeding more than twice the OECD average of 14.66%. Although male NEET rates in Türkiye also surpass OECD levels, the gap is less pronounced; 21.59% of men aged 20-24 are NEET, compared to an average of 13.31% across the OECD (OECD, 2022). Additionally, 38.58% of Turkish men aged 25-34 possess a tertiary education degree, slightly below the OECD average of 41.09% (OECD, 2022).

Despite the fact that participation in higher education has grown in Türkiye, young people especially women continue to face significant hurdles in translating educational accomplishment into employment opportunities. Altogether, these indicators emphasise the urgent necessity for targeted policies in Türkiye to tackle gender-based inequalities, huge number of youth unemployment, and the continuous misalignment between education and labour market demands. Lowering the NEET rate and increasing the socioeconomic view of young people requires expanding high-quality vocational training, strengthening women's access to higher education, and promoting inclusive employment strategies.

5. YOUTH UNEMPLOYMENT IN TUNISIA

According to ILO In Tunisia, the unemployment rate among young people especially university graduates continually increased 30%. This is largely due to a conflict between educational output and labour market needs.

Below graph shows Tunisia's youth unemployment rate from 1991 to 2023. It illustrates the percentage of young people, usually aged 15 to 24, who are unemployed but looking for work. By presenting a long-term time series, the graph enables us to track the response of youth unemployment to structural economic changes, crises and policy reforms over more than three decades.

It shows a relatively stable pattern of around 30-32% during the 1990s and early 2000s. However, a significant increase occurred after the global economic crisis of 2008, with

youth unemployment reaching a dramatic peak of over 42% in 2011. Although there was a partial decline in subsequent years, unemployment rates remained elevated and volatile throughout the 2010s and early 2020s, reflecting ongoing economic challenges, labour market mismatches and demographic pressures. The recent upward trend, especially after 2018, signals ongoing challenges for young people trying to transition into stable employment.

Overall, this visual trend highlights youth unemployment as a long-standing structural issue in Turkey, strongly linked to broader economic instability. Persistently high youth unemployment rates increase the risk of young people becoming NEET, which can result in long-term social and economic exclusion.

Figure 1. Youth Unemployment in Tunisia from 1991 to 2024.

Statista. (2025). Youth unemployment rate in Tunisia from 1991 to 2024.

The graph above shows that youth unemployment in Tunisia has increased significantly over the last three decades. Youth unemployment peaked particularly in 2011, and it is impossible to comprehend this increase without considering the factors that contributed to it: Two significant incidents are particularly noteworthy. The initial start of the events

of the Spring Revolution was the self-immolation of a 26-year-old Tunisian vendor, Mohamed Bouazizi, in December 2010. The act that caused millions of protests was led by the experience of one vendor who faced financial challenges yet chose to pursue any job that gave him his daily bread. Moreover, he got mistreated by a law enforcer, Fayda Hamdi, who confiscated his belongings for not having the permit to sell within a specific area. Furthermore, this led the desperate vendor to fight back verbally only to get humiliated by the inspector. According to witnesses, the individual in question made a sarcastic remark in a state of frustration prior to being subjected to a public slap, which was considered the pinnacle of humiliation. To obtain justice, he approached the local government and demanded a meeting with the governor, threatening self-immolation if his demand was not met. It is evident that no one responded to the appeal. In a desperate act, Bouazizi set himself on fire in front of the government building.

Secondly, unethical hiring practices by the Gafsa Phosphate Company (GPC) triggered the protests that erupted in Redeyef, Gafsa -around 300 kilometres from Tunis- in January 2008. What began as labour protests quickly evolved into a broader political uprising against the Ben Ali regime. Police use of lethal force against demonstrators further intensified public anger and fueled resistance. Although authorities moved quickly to contain the unrest and prevent its spread, tensions remained high. In the months that followed, Ben Ali managed to suppress the uprising in Redeyef with the support of security forces. Yet violence persisted elsewhere: two young men, Mohamed Ammari and Chawki Hidri, both 18 years old, were shot and killed by security forces in Menzel Bouzaiene. Despite temporary repression, widespread dissatisfaction continued to grow, eventually leading to mass demonstrations that contributed to a government shutdown and rising economic pressures.

Following these events, unemployment surged sharply, and the lack of regulatory oversight encouraged a manipulative market strategy often described as “boycott until prices rise, then release and repeat.” This dynamic yielded two major consequences: it fueled inflation and exacerbated internal challenges for both the government and the

general population. After the revolution, widespread institutional dysfunction and the disruption of public services plunged the country into disorder, forcing many businesses to shut down. As a result, large numbers of workers lost their jobs, further deepening the unemployment crisis.

To illustrate this point, it is important to note that prior to the revolution, politics was held in high esteem, and the former Ben Ali regime was widely feared. Prices were regulated, and 20 TND sufficed to procure groceries for a family unit. However, as a result of the high rate of unemployment, by 2025, 20 TND could only purchase a quick meal for one person.

When considering the evidence in its entirety, the 2011 surge in youth unemployment can be understood as a consequence of long-standing social unrest and economic injustice, rather than an isolated incident. This understanding allows us to interpret the revolution as a response to these underlying causes, rather than as a random event. While the movement may have catalysed political reforms, it concomitantly exerted deleterious effects on employment opportunities and social interactions.

According to (Blanchard and Wolfers, 2000), Tunisia's labour laws haven't altered since the 1990s, and there are institutions that could account for variations in employment dynamics (Vacher, Jérôme, and Aymen, 2023). Highly believed that structural factors, such as inflexible labour market regulations, limited financial resources, and lacklustre product market competition, are to blame for the rise in unemployment over the past few decades, however, they noted that when they examined the labour market policies, they discover that the costs and procedures associated with firing people are primarily responsible for the unemployment rate: They both agreed that lower unemployment rates are linked to lower firing rates and lower compensation expenses for departed workers.

"Among all institutional factors, the deterioration of product market regulation is likely to be the most relevant factor. During the 2009-2017 period, and despite the adoption of

important laws to strengthen the business climate (e.g., the revision of the competition law in 2015 and a new investment law in 2016), improved transparency and a decrease in trade tariffs, several product market and business regulations' indicators in Tunisia (based on surveys) experienced a deterioration." (Vacher, Jérôme and Aymen, 2023, 14). Both authors discovered that the actions of oligopolies and monopolies over the past ten years were what strengthened the decline in administrative requirements and competition. For example, administrative requirements are rules and bureaucratic procedures that companies must follow to operate legally, even though the only objective is to legalize the Tunisian economy and its elements. However, when these procedures become too time-consuming or complex, they become obstacles.

Regarding the decline in competition, it makes sense to assume that, given the monopolization of the market by powerful entities like large corporations, this will only lead to a lower rate of competition because new competitors will fall short of the current level of competition. It will also result in fewer innovations and a decline in efficiency, which will reduce job opportunities and diversification, ultimately supporting the private sector's dominance in the monopolized market.

The impact of institutional factors on the increase of unemployment in Tunisia between 2009 and 2017 is more pronounced for males than for females (Vacher, Jérôme and Aymen, 2023). However, another case study by the world bank, highlighted that regional disparities exacerbate the female employment mentioning the rural females being the most affected; "Female employment is particularly low in the south (8.3 percent in rural areas and 17.2 percent in urban areas) and in the interior region (16.1 percent in rural areas and 34.3 percent in urban areas), compared with young women working in the coastal region (27.5 percent in rural areas and 45.9 percent in urban areas)" (World Bank, 2013).

Furthermore, the World Bank highlighted that a 2013 study found that a person's likelihood of finding work is strongly correlated with their wealth and family connection

status. “Regression analysis suggests that paternal education counts more than a young person's own education in determining whether the young person finds work, while household wealth also appears to play a strong role” (World Bank, 2013).

Tunisian government has implemented the CIVP (The Contract for Professional Integration) program, which incentivizes private companies to employ recent graduates on the condition that the government covers a portion of their salaries for a period of two years. This strategy lowers unemployment while promoting success for the public and private sectors as well as students. For instance, student salaries will contribute to the government's social coffers after they are paid out, but for the time being, they are a valuable resource that supports the expansion of government funds. The students will contribute to the economy and other sectors by paying for their tuition, expenses, and transportation. Because they will pay less, private sector employers are more likely to hire a degree-holding graduate than a non-graduate student. In the end, the student will gain some experience that will prepare him to shape his career for the two years of CIVP. Even though the contract's duration has been shortened to one year since the start of 2023, it is still a one-way vocational training opportunity that allows students to obtain experience instead of going jobless.

Another practice by the government on the north coast of Tunisia, a sustainable agriculture project combines organic techniques, efficient water management, and training for small farmers. This initiative has increased productivity, reduced pesticide use, and created green jobs, especially for rural women and youth (IEMed, 2024). The project's success lies in its community-based approach and the collaboration between NGOs, local authorities, and international organizations, demonstrating how decentralization and social inclusion can be key to the green transition.

6. CONFLICT BETWEEN EDUCATION AND LABOUR MARKET NEEDS

One of the most critical drivers of youth unemployment in both Tunisia and Türkiye is the ongoing mismatch between educational outcomes and labour market demands. Although university enrolment rates are relatively high in both countries, a substantial proportion of graduates struggle to secure employment aligned with their skills and qualifications, especially in disciplines such as engineering, information technology, and the social sciences.

In Tunisia, the economy has not diversified enough to absorb the growing number of degree holders. Consequently, this led to many professionals and talented youngsters remaining either unemployed, underpaid, or undervalued, as the open positions that are left to be filled within the economy don't require the needed education level, nor do they elevate the human potential of a youth to participate in a bigger role within the society; hence, we come up with a loss of human capital and personal frustrations among young people.

Türkiye, on the other hand, has a similar challenge; although the education sector is well developed and well established, it lacks diversification in terms of what is within the economy market. For instance, education is expanding; however, if we follow the flow of young graduates, we will conclude that job creation has not met the pace needed to match what higher education is preparing for. As a result, we have a surplus of qualified individuals, while some industries are in need of skilled labor in particular fields like technical or vocational fields, which leads to more struggle in finding the perfect candidate, not to forget the qualification and training needed to establish the integration of them.

Another major point that contributes to the mismatch of jobs in both Tunisia and Türkiye is the lack of coordination between the academical field, in other words universities, and the industries that are employee hunting. To explain further, there were no highly qualified programs like internships or mid-transition certifications or apprenticeships that prepare the youth to enter the market and compensate for their lack of expertise.

Contrary to Tunisia and Türkiye, Germany and Switzerland have facilitated the integration of their youth through vocational education training that was integrated into their teaching, facilitating the transitioning of youth. Neither Türkiye nor Tunisia reached far in integrating these models or bridging their education and unemployment. Therefore, the absence of a structured work-based environment created a lack of expertise in terms of soft skills as well as a lack of experience for newly graduated students, which, on the other hand, leaves employers with less choice to choose from when recruiting.

Moreover, Tunisia and Türkiye often relied on the public sector to recruit and fill the gaps created by the mismatch of education and the labor market; however, due to economic constraints, hiring freezes during corona, and other matters like public debt, the power of the public sector has diminished, leaving the surplus of youth left aside for unemployment, and it also created more competition in the private sector job hunting. For instance, we mentioned before that holding companies tend to have power due to capitalism and dominance over the sectors, and this was enforced more by the weakness of the public sector and the lack of coordination of the academic and industrial fields.

Based on the OECD report (2022), Türkiye's main challenge of mismatch between education and employment was translated into the failure of the educational system to equip young people with the specific skills required to excel in the needed economical fields, especially when we talk about renewable energy, environmental management, and waste recycling sectors.

Even though the government tried to diminish the issue and reduce the gap between what we have and what we need, the alignment of education and the market didn't go as planned, as there is a noticeable gap between qualifications that are being taught and given and the green economy needs. This discrepancy makes it harder for youth to participate in green jobs even though the demand for them is getting higher. The OECD report provides strong support for our main argument of labor and education mismatch,

highlighting the negative effects it has had on the youth and presenting the specialized training certification programs as a way to solve the issue, particularly in renewable energy aspects where specific and unique skills are required.

The Türkiye education system is still relying on traditional fields due to the nature of Türkiye's economy; it relies basically on fields that will enforce its medical tourism and therefore less diversification in terms of choice. The education system doesn't fully integrate sustainable sectors in renewable energy, which supports our argument. This misalignment is the main cause of why young youth struggle to adapt and enroll in renewable energy sectors, for which skills are highly required to be in the workforce.

The OECD further elaborates that it is important to implement technical and vocational education and training programs (TVET) in its own educational system; thus, with its own absence, the gap between the labor market and education widens. Despite the awareness of youth in regard to it, it is still a challenge to work on. Thus, the findings align with the argument that education and jobs mismatch hinders youth employment in renewable energy sectors.

Moving on, the UNDP report (2024) further supports our argument regarding the misalignment of jobs and education, taking Türkiye's economy as an example. The UNDP report (2024) supported that even though the future of green jobs is further increasing, the lag created from not having youth prepared to seize these opportunities further slows the economy within Türkiye. The report stresses the importance of adapting education and vocational training within the process of education and job creation in order to be able to participate in emerging roles in emerging green sectors such as renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, and waste management. Furthermore, it suggests the establishment of specialized training programs and green certifications, which will eventually bridge the gap and improve the outcome of the sustainable sectors. The report highlights the importance of green policies, in which it will facilitate the establishment of

these training opportunities for the youth; by doing this, Türkiye can increase its green economy and reduce any gap led by education and the labor market.

These policies can only be successful with the support of the government, which will further reduce the burden on the public sector while creating a balance between public and private. As for Tunisia, the OECD report of 2022 highlights that for Tunisia's case, the youth are struggling to enter these green job opportunities, as while there is an advancement in the technical training and vocational education, the system itself does not meet the qualification to enter green sectors, while the training might exist Tunisia's development in terms of the green sector mainly relies on the sector as a holding for income, while agriculture tends to be taking less attention in terms of investments. In conclusion, while there is progress in establishing a green economy, especially in agriculture, Tunisia's system still needs further improvement in highlighting and integrating the green economy within the education system to reduce the limitation for the youth in the green economy.

The report also illustrates how the facts mentioned previously hinder youth employment, and it demands to highlight the core issues within the educational system, suggesting that a full review is needed. For instance, talking as a student that lived within Tunisia, I can only testify that the education manuals weren't as customized to what the market needed but rather to what the university had open, creating first a surplus of youth that market cannot absorb, preparing them for unemployment, and on the other hand less educational manuals and road that involve the green sector was available for selection. While farming and agriculture are growing, educational roads and technical training aren't there at the level to support the green sector, resulting in capitalism within the private sector and competition between employees with the same qualifications to keep their positions or to hunt for one. It is also creating a brain drain; therefore, immigration and a loss of potential and qualifications to foreign countries.

Furthermore, the reports highlight the importance of addressing this mismatch between education and the labor market through targeted segments from the government. While coordination is necessary between the public and private sectors, having policies that support education and reduce job mismatch will improve Tunisia's integration in the green sector.

GREENSTEP is one of the successful initiatives that demonstrated the positive impact of specialized training on youth for green sectors; having Tunisia follow such an initiative can only result in reducing the barriers of implementation and increasing the chances of entry for the youth to renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, and waste management sectors, thus a better future for the workforce.

The European Training Foundation (ETF) report (2024) supported that while Tunisia has expanded its own vocational training, it is still lacking and not tailored to green jobs specifications. It emphasized that Tunisia's vocational education and training (VET) needs to be better equipped in order to have proper training opportunities for the youth. The report strongly suggests that specialized training programs and green certifications are needed to reduce the gap between education and the labor market, thus enabling a more swift access for young entries to the green market. Furthermore, it advocates that these programs can boost employment toward a more sustainable path; however, this can only be done through a strong partnership between schools and industry while relying mainly on the government's presence and policies to facilitate functioning and integration. As a conclusion, these trainings will improve the green life within Tunisia and increase its own youth participation.

Finally, the education and job incompatibility is a widely recognized problem that impacts the young people's ability to find work in the green sector in particular. Many sources support the argument of skills mismatch and education while reinforcing the idea that the lack of specialized training is the main reason for the continuation of this challenge in Tunisia and Türkiye

7. THE POTENTIAL OF GREEN JOBS TO REDUCE YOUTH UNEMPLOYMENT

The green transition presents significant opportunities for youth, as emerging green industries expand and demand a highly skilled workforce. Advances in technology are creating new career pathways in renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, green construction, and environmental protection, offering increased labour market entry points for young people with relevant technical expertise. These developments not only support environmental sustainability but also reinforce the shift toward cleaner and more accessible energy systems. Sectors such as solar, wind, geothermal, and hydropower are expected to become major economic drivers as the green economy gains broader recognition.

A key component of this transformation is green manufacturing, which prioritizes the use of recycled materials and environmentally responsible production processes. This approach aims to reduce ecological harm while helping to combat pollution and conserve natural resources. Similarly, organic farming, agroforestry, and ecotechnology are becoming essential pillars of sustainable food systems.

Sustainable planning is also crucial in managing this transition, as it must address challenges such as climate change, resource scarcity, and rapid urbanization. This includes expanding green buildings, smart transportation networks, and energy-efficient housing. Ultimately, innovation will serve as the foundation of success in the green economy, driving advancements in waste reduction and resource efficiency and supporting long-term environmental resilience.

Furthermore, equipping young people with the necessary skills to participate in the green economy requires the expansion of green education and vocational training programs. Strong collaboration among governments, industry stakeholders, and educational institutions is essential to design training pathways that align with evolving labour market needs. In addition, youth-focused green policies and improved access to financial support,

such as startup funding, can empower young entrepreneurs and contribute to the development of an inclusive and dynamic green business ecosystem (Öz et al., 2019).

As environmental awareness increases, youth can take advantage of the market's growing interest in sustainability to build businesses that contribute to both economic and environmental goals, this will enable them to develop innovative green technologies and services in areas such as clean tech, eco-tourism, and sustainable fashion.

The Sustainable Agriculture Project in Tunisia aimed to empower youth employment by giving them more freedom. The program's target was rural areas and women in these areas, which targeted a specific social demographic. As a result, the program qualified people for green certification programs related to agriculture. Based on this, we validated Sen's Capability Approach by expanding people's freedom and access to resources. We also validated the signalling theory because the green certification program helped youth show off their skills in the up-and-coming sector and validated the capability approach theory regarding the special skills that young people must master in these programs to excel in green jobs. Finally, the government was present to facilitate youth participation in these programs and projects, especially in rural areas and women validating the institutional theory. These results demonstrate that green investment, institution involvement, green certification programs, and labour-education alignment can all contribute to a decrease in youth unemployment.

8. CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between youth unemployment and the emerging green economy in Tunisia and Türkiye, highlighting both the challenges and the opportunities associated with integrating young job seekers into sustainable labour markets. The analysis demonstrated that institutional reforms, particularly the introduction of green certifications and supportive policy frameworks, have the potential to significantly improve young people's skills, employability, and competitiveness in green sectors. Additionally, the findings emphasize the influence of cultural and societal

norms in shaping young people's career decisions, especially in newly developing fields such as renewable energy and sustainable production.

Despite progress made in both countries, substantial barriers remain. Regional inequalities, gender imbalances, and insufficient access to targeted skill development programs continue to limit career transitions into green jobs. Bridging this gap requires comprehensive and inclusive policies that address labour market mismatches while enhancing youth participation in the green transition.

The study also acknowledges broader systemic constraints, noting that global economic priorities do not yet fully recognize green industries as central to development strategies. This structural challenge disproportionately affects developing economies like Tunisia and Türkiye, where young, educated individuals often struggle to convert their skills into meaningful employment due to slow sectoral transformation. A strategic shift is therefore essential. Building strong green industries with forward looking labour market policies will determine whether the next generation can actively contribute to sustainable development rather than being left behind during the transition.

Lastly, this research underscores the need for continued investigation into innovative approaches that tackle youth unemployment within the context of the green economy. Future studies should explore regional policies, educational reforms, and cross-country comparisons to better understand the global dynamics of green job creation and youth integration. Strengthening this body of knowledge will be crucial in ensuring that the green economy evolves as both an environmental necessity and a source of inclusive, long-term socioeconomic opportunity.

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